

Crop Diversification Pattern Based on Bhatia's Method: A Geographical Analysis of Latur and Aurangabad Agriculture Division

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Abstract:

In the view of agriculture performance there are many components to clarify the status of performing agriculture. Earlier data of agriculture sector sees 11.7% growth, from 6.1% in 2019-20 agriculture sector is likely to report a whopping 11.7% growth in 2020-21. The three agriculture strategy of extensive farming, intensive agriculture and technical change it is technical change which is universally accepted as the best strategy (Desai 1997). The performance rate or ratio of state in not stable for long period, because it can be important to observed that, Deccan plateau constitutes 50 percent of the Drought-prone area, 12 percent of the population lives in drought prone area, deficient rainfall once in 5 years. The 1996 drought affected 7 districts 266.75 lakh people, 1997 affected 17 districts and in 2001 droughts affected over 23 districts includes 20,000 villages. Around 4.5 million hectares of crops was affected in the State. Rainfall is main source of water. Therefore, here an attempt has been made to examine the agriculture performance for the development of agriculture area.

In the recent view the agriculture need is beginning to be felt its ensuring food security is the main intention on agriculture development and fulfill of this target farmers and researchers and policy makers are achieving together green revolution. For the more productivity and production, it should adopt new technologies, varieties and new scientific cropping patterns. Also, in this context Niti Aayog reported 10.41 percent annual growth rate is requires increasing in farmer's income till 2022-23, therefore its must to strengthen agriculture source of growth in income as well as other sources. Government agriculture and related agencies also focus on diversification towards high value crop.

Keywords: Spatial Variation, Agriculture Performance Index, Irrigation etc.

Introduction:

Crop diversification refers to raising a variety of crops on arable land. Generally it is observed that more number of crops in a combination; indicate the greater degree of crop diversification (Ayyar, 1969). Crop diversification is a common phenomenon in Indian conditions because the farmers try to satisfy most of family demand from its own land resulted into crop diversification. (Jasbir Singh, 1976). Crop diversification in India is generally viewed as a shift from traditionally grown less remunerative crops to more remunerative crops or cropping pattern. (Hazra, 2001).

Climate, Economic and Technical factors output reflect on crop diversification. Sustainable source of irrigation, Physical location, farmer's attitude for crop selection and Government policy plays important role to place crop diversification. Cost of advance equipment and infrastructure, stability in production and profitability stimulus crop diversification. Such as Pulses and sugarcane replaced by oilseed like soybean in latur and aurangabad agriculture division. In Latur agriculture division Economic, industrial,

educational, social development of this area is dependent on agricultural production and agriculture is the major occupation of majority of the population.

Study Area:

Latur agriculture division includes Latur, Osmanabad, Nanded, Parbhani and Hingoli five districts and Aurangabad agriculture division includes Aurangabad, Jalna and Beed Districts. Latur and Aurangabad is an administrative headquarter of agriculture division, in south Maharashtra. It has an area of Latur 36099 sq. kms and Aurangabad 28480 sq. kms. The average annual rainfall is 367 mm and temperature is 27 °C.

Objective:

To examine pattern of crop diversification in Latur agriculture division.

Data Base and Methodology:

The Study is based on the secondary data. The following methodology has been implemented for the present study.

S.S Bhatia's Crop diversification method:

To understand crop diversification, S.S. Bhatia method to measure degree of crop diversification is adopted. This method gives

$$\text{Crop diversification Index} = \frac{\text{Percentage of sown area under 'n' crop}}{\text{Number of 'n' crops}}$$

Where,

'n' = signify the crops which are individually occupy 10 percent or more of the gross cropped area.

Result and Discussion:

Regional pattern of crop diversification in the Latur agriculture division is categorized in high, moderate and

a constructive, suitable for measuring the degree of diversification in cropping pattern. A specific procedure of method is used for crop selection as follows:

Total crops divided by the total area (Divide 100 by n). 'N' number of crops grown in area. Then consider only those crops cover an area more than 100/N. Among them rest of crops which are less than 100/N are ignored. Here selected 10 major crops for the purpose and ignored the crops with less than 10 percentage of sown area.

low diversification Zones. A region view of these zones is shown in Map 2. (Crop Diversification map).

Table No. 1
Index of crop diversification in various Districts in Latur & Sambhajinagar
Agriculture Division
 (2020-21)

District	No. of Crop	Area (%)	Index of Diversification
Aurangabad	1	57.26	57.26
Jalna	2	65.34	32.67
Beed	2	66.72	33.36
Latur	4	90.51	22.63
Osmanabad	3	69.00	23.00
Nanded	3	75.06	25.02
Parbhani	3	74.60	24.87
Hingoli	2	59.48	29.74

Source: Compile by author.

Table No. 2
Level of Diversification (2020-21)

Level of Diversification	Range	District
High	Less than 24.41	Latur, Osmanabad
Moderate	24.41 to 26.18	Nanded, Parbhani
Low	More than 26.18	Aurangabad, Jalna, Beed & Hingoli

Source: Compile by author.

The district-wise regional pattern of diversity is based on 10 crops that most of the districts drop under the category of high diversification producing number of crops.

Crop diversification at 2020-21, there was a notable variant in crops diversity reported. Now regional diversification pattern of crop diversification describe into three level of diversification. High level of

diversification (below 24.41), moderate level diversification (24.41 to 26.18%) and low level of diversification (more than 26.18%). Regionally High level of diversification were observed in Latur and Osmanabad district in Latur Division. Improvement in micro irrigation facilities, availability market, infrastructural development and changing attitude of farmers towards traditional

methods in farming are main reasons responsible for change in crop diversification. Moderate level diversification was observed in Nanded and Parbhani district. Low level diversification was found in Aurangabad, Jalna, Beed in aurangabad division & Hingoli district in Latur division with large area under soybean and cotton crop.

Adopting new advance agricultural technology high yielding varieties, chemical and bio fertilizers use and mechanization pattern of crops diversifications may be classified as field crops, plantations crops, commercial crops, floricultural crops, plants and etc. Current era in Latur agricultural division production agriculture which includes soybean, grapes, sugarcane, and floriculture has been major impact able elements for diversification.

Latur and Nanded districts agriculture is diversifying to high value food commodities, this show that there is huge implementation of crop diversification. The level of agricultural productivity as a concept means the degree to which the economic, cultural, technical and organizational variables are also to exploit the biotic resources of the area for agricultural production (Singh, J. 1984). The area under cultivation and production of kharif-rabbi, seasonal and perennial affected but using and adopting techniques and technology farmers achieve their diversification. Sometimes the area under soybean and sugarcane crops varies according to the availability of irrigation. Farmers take advantage of micro irrigation with help of canal and other sources especially in Aurangabad, Jalna, Beed & Hingoli district for diversifying crop area.

Conclusion:

In Latur and Aurangabad agriculture division, Latur and Osmanabad district agricultural is diversification to high value. Moderate to low level area of crops diversification was registered in Nanded and Parbhani in 2020-21. Latur and Osmanabad district is outlook as changing from traditionally to more gainful crops. The input of crop diversification in agricultural growth is major. The study has examined, crop diversification is the solution of many gaining problems. In the rain fed area bust by green revolution stage. It can be used as impact able determines to evaluate rural poverty and usually rural employment and

safeguard natural resources. Therefore, more training for the advanced techniques of irrigation such as drip, sprinklers etc. for right and sufficient use of water and decreases threat of salinities. Aurangabad, Beed & Hingoli have most scarcity during summer season. Issue of soil degradation, Use of organic manures and fertilizers. Achieve agricultural diversification, focus on one multiple factors. This means increasing irrigation diversity productivity by implementing irrigation, modern technology, high yielding seeds, new crop models and change in cropping patterns. It should be adopted and understand for mortared and low diversifying area.

References:

- 1) Bhatia, S.S., (1965): Patterns of Crop Concentration and Diversification in India, *Economic Geography*, 41, pp. 40-56.
- 2) Dutta, A.k. And Sen Gupta R (1969): An Assessment of Agricultural Development in West Bengal. *The Journal of Tropical Geography*, Vol. 128.
- 3) Ayyar, N.P.,(1969): Crop Regions of Madhya Pradesh, A Study in Methodology, *Geographical Review of India*, Vol.31, No. 1, pp. 1-19.
- 4) Jasbir Singh, (1976): "An Agricultural Geography of Haryana", Kurukshetra, Vishal Publications, pp. 131-138, 187-190.
- 5) Vidyanath V. (1985) Agricultural Productivity in Andhra Pradesh, the *National Geographical Journal of India*, Vol. 31T. Mahendran (2008) Agriculture development in India, Abhijeet Publication Delhi.
- 6) Rubina Khanam1, Debarati Bhaduri2 and A. K. Nayak3 (January 2018) *Indian Farming* 68 (01): 31–32;
- 7) Comprehensive District Agriculture Plan, Osmanabad.